

Project acronym: SURE-Farm

Project no.: 727520

Start date of project: June 2017

Duration: 4 years

Annex D7.3 -Execution report 01.06.2017-30.05.2021

D7.3: Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan.

Work Performed by Partner 9, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

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Due date	30 th May 2021
Version/Date	To be updated periodically (living document)
Work Package	WP7
Task	T 7.1
Task lead	P9 in close collaboration with P1 and contribution from other partners
Dissemination level	Public

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1 Means of verification – Communication and Dissemination tools

This document is an Annex to the D7.3. Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan. The aim of this document is to check the means of verification of the communication and dissemination activities performed under the dissemination, exploitation and communication plan.

The following table details the means of verification defined at the beginning of the project (D7.3-31.08.2017 (<https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/D7.3-Dissemination-exploitation-and-communication-plan-Version-31-August-2017.pdf>) and reached at 30.05.2021.

Milestone title	Means of verification		
		Defined at 31.08.2017	Reached 30.05.2021
		7	
Social media penetration	Number of tweets per year Number of followers per year Number of likes per year (*)	250 300 200	332 (Figure 1) 596 (Figure 1) 1.116 (Figure 1) (Section 2. Detailed communication report)
Communication strategy and execution plan, drafted and approved by consortium	Communication strategy and execution plan	1	1 (D7.3- v.30.08.3017: https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/D7.3-Dissemination-exploitation-and-communication-plan-Version-31-August-2017.pdf)
Website	Number of website visitors per month (*)	600	550 (Section 2. Detailed communication report).
Co-creation platform (virtual, local, central)	Number of actors Local co-creation workshops/focu	50 24	60 (D.7.3-v.30.05.2020: https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Annex.-D7.3-Execution-report-01.12.19-31.05.2020.pdf) 48 (workshops on current resilience, workshops on resilience in the future, focus group on improved risk management tools, focus groups on improved policies, workshops on implementation roadmaps)

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	s groups organised	4	4 (Consortium meetings and Final Scientific Seminar)
	Central co-creation meetings held		
Open access report	Number of open report published	21	33 https://www.surefarmproject.eu/deliverables/publications/
Refereed articles published	Number of referred articles published	9	32 (Detail in section 3.1 and https://www.surefarmproject.eu/deliverables/spin-off-papers/)
Tool protocols published	Number of tool protocols published	2	2 https://www.surefarmproject.eu/deliverables/tools/
Open access book	Number of open access book published	1	1 Details in D 7.6 (https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/D7.6-Edited-book.pdf)
Press release	Number of press release published	2	2 https://www.surefarmproject.eu/deliverables/policybusiness-briefs-and-short-communications/
Infographics developed	Number of infographics disseminated	12	14 (infographics, GIFs and videos) https://www.surefarmproject.eu/digital-materials/
Policy briefs published	Number of policy briefs disseminated	8	9 (8 policy brief and 1 short communication) https://www.surefarmproject.eu/deliverables/policybusiness-briefs-and-short-communications/
Business briefs published	Number of business disseminated	2	2 https://www.surefarmproject.eu/deliverables/policybusiness-briefs-and-short-communications/
Midterm scientific seminar held	Publication on website/ social media	5	1 publication on website/ 21 posts on social media
	Agenda	1	1 (https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/Agenda_Mid-term-Scientific-Seminar.pdf)
		30	

D7.3 Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan

	Attendants registered		45 (D7.4: https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/D7.4_Mi-term-and-final-scientific-seminar-.pdf)
	Conclusions written	1	-
	Presentations gathered	15	10 https://www.surefarmproject.eu/deliverables/scientific-seminars/
	Number of videos	3	10 https://www.surefarmproject.eu/deliverables/scientific-seminars/
	Number of photos	10	6 (https://www.surefarmproject.eu/deliverables/scientific-seminars/
Final scientific seminar held	Publication on the website/ social media	5	1 publication on website/ 23 posts on social media
	Agenda	1	1 https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Final-program-SURE-Farm-and-EAAE-seminar-Mornings-of-18-19-20-May_17.05.2021.pdf
	Attendants registered	30	97 (D7.4: https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/D7.4_Mi-term-and-final-scientific-seminar-.pdf)
	Conclusions written	1	-
	Presentations gathered	15	12 (4 presentations with no ppt) https://www.surefarmproject.eu/deliverables/scientific-seminars/
	Videos	3	4 https://www.surefarmproject.eu/deliverables/scientific-seminars/
	Photo Gallery	10	13 (https://www.surefarmproject.eu/deliverables/scientific-seminars/
Dissemination activities	Dissemination events / People reached	-	90 events/ 4.866 people (Section 3) C:\Users\dinie\ownCloud\SURE-Farm\9_Work Packages\WP7_Dissemination,exploitation and Communication\Table of outreach.xlsx

(*) The first social media were launched within the six first months of the project. The number of years considered is 3.5 years.

Figure 1. Social media screenshot at 30.05.2021

2 Detailed communication report-2017-2021

1. Executive summary

1.1 Web traffic

Data analysis of SURE-FARM Project's web (<https://www.surefarmproject.eu/>) covers the period from November 2017 (activity beginning) to June 31st 2020.

This report provides:

- **Audience Data:** page visits, sessions, bounce rate, pages per session, duration rate, visitors and new visitors.
- **Acquisition Data** (traffic origin): organic sessions (through Google searches), direct (<https://www.surefarmproject.eu/>), referral (by links from other sites) and social (from social media).
- **Data graphics** on the origin of the sessions and the demographic profile of visitors.

During the development of the web's activity, 68.513 pages have been visited, there have been 29.291 sessions and 17.600 visitors. The bounce rate of the period has been 53,91%.

The highest number of visited pages was achieved in April 2018 (2.679) and the lowest in January 2021 (598), (setting aside November 2017, when the activity began: 414 visited pages). The highest number of sessions was achieved in January 2020 (1.216) and the lowest in January 2021 (237).

During the analysed period, the average of pages per session was 2,34 and the average time was 2 minutes and 41 seconds.

47,31% of the web traffic is organic, 37,15 % is direct, 7,93 % comes from social media and 7,20 % is referral.

The country with more sessions is Spain (16,21%), followed by USA (10,45%), Germany (10,42%), Netherlands (9,83%)

and Belgium (6,65%). In terms of demographic variables, there are more male visitors (52,1%) than female ones (47,9%) and most visitors are in the age range of 25 - 34 years old.

During the analyzed period there is an upward trend with respect to page visits, sessions and visitors, and a downward trend with respect to number of pages per session and time per page.

1.1.1 2017

First data: November 2017. The most significant aspects this year are average time per session in November (almost five minutes and a half), which is the best result of all the analyzed months, and the relevance of direct traffic, which is higher than the organic one: 57,81% v. 36,65 %.

1.1.2 2018

20.089 visited pages, 7.833 sessions and 4.555 visitors. This is the year with more referral traffic. Let us highlight the number of visited pages in April (2.679), and the average time per session in February (4 minutes and 7 seconds, with an average of 3,33 visited pages).

1.1.3 2019

21.322 visited pages, 6% more than the former year, 8.919 sessions (14% more) and 5.256 visitors. 2019 has the best average time per page, almost three minutes, and also the highest traffic from social media (923 sessions).

1.1.4 2020

21.636 visited pages (1% more than 2019); 10.022 sessions (12% more) and 6.446 visitors. 2020 has the largest number of direct sessions (4.108), almost as many as the organic ones (4.634). January 2020 is the month with more sessions, most of them direct ones (60%).

1.1.5 2021

The report only includes the first quarter of 2021.

1.2 Social Media

The report includes the social media that have been used by SURE - Farm: Twitter, Instagram and LinkedIn.

1.2.1 Twitter

The profile was set in June 2017 and started its activity in September of that year. Since then it has achieved 1.181 followers, it has published 443 tweets with 590.068 impressions and 7923 interactions, 3.567 of which are likes. Since september 2019 there have been 6.262 visits to the page and it has been mentioned 265 times.

Interactions show a clearly upward trend.

1.2.1.1 2017

At the end of the year the page had 135 followers, 12 tweets and 18.105 impressions. Interactions: 110 likes, 110 retweets, 5 replies and 120 clicks in the posts' links.

1.2.1.2 2018

At the end of the year the page had 442 followers (227,41% more than the year before). It published 41 tweets, which achieved 1.320 interactions (483 likes, 346 retweets, 15 replies and 494 clicks).

1.2.1.3 2019

By December 31st the page had 778 followers (76,02% more than the year before). It published 172 tweets, which had 239.974 impressions, the highest number of the analyzed period. Interactions: 3.312 (1.611 likes, 748 retweets, 11 replies and 942 clicks).

Since September 2019, Twitter records visits to the page (807 until December 31st), and mentions (27).

1.2.1.4 2020

At the end of 2020, SURE - Farm's profile had 1.109 followers, an increase of 42,54% over the previous year. It published 171 Tweets, with 182.065 impressions. Those posts received 1.037 likes, 415 retweets and 703 clicks. There were 2.687 visits and 161 mentions.

1.2.1.5 2021

By March 31st, the page had 1.181 followers (6,49% more), and 47 posts with 718 interactions, 2.728 visits and 47 mentions.

1.2.2. Instagram

The profile was set in August 2017, but it didn't have any further activity until January 2019. Since then, it has got 227 followers, and published 233 posts with 1.955 interactions, 1.898 of which are likes. Besides, there have been 880 video views.

1.2.2.1 2019

At the end of 2019, the page had 85 followers, 98 posts, 1.003 likes and 463 video views. In February 2019 it got the highest number of likes in the analyzed period, with 191 likes.

1.2.2.2 2020

By December 31st 2020, the page had 201 followers (136,47% more than the previous year). It published 107 posts with 669 interactions and 339 video views.

1.2.2.3 2021

By the end of March there were 277 followers, 37,81% more than the previous year. In these three months 27 posts were published, with 228 interactions, 227 of which were likes, and 83 video views.

1.2.3. LinkedIn

The profile was set in January 2020 and started its activity in March.

From November 3rd 2020 until April 29th 2021 an advertising campaign was developed in order to get more followers. It lasted 107 days, alternating a fortnight of promotion and a week off. With a total investment of 1.589,00€, the page got 105 direct followers and 156 indirect followers.

1.2.3.1 2020

By December 31st 2020, the page had 300 followers and 40 posts, with 394 clicks on the posts' links, 301 reactions and 52 shares. Since April, the page has had 26 unique visitors and 553 total visits.

1.2.3.2 2021

By March 31st, the page had 496 followers (65,33% increase), 13 posts, 21 clicks and 21 interactions (150 reactions, 58 shares and 3 comments). In this period, the profile received 294 unique visitors and 520 visits.

When the last ad campaign finished (April 29th), the page had 584 followers (94,67% increase over the previous year).

2. SURE - Farm website. Trend 2017 - 2021

2.1 Total visits.

2.2 Total sessions- , organic sessions - , direct sessions - and referral sessions -

2.3 Total Bounce rate - , organic - , direct - and referral -

2.4 Pages per session.

2.5 Average Session duration

2.6 Total visitors

3. SURE - Social media. Trend 2017 - 2021

3.1 Twitter. Followers

3.2 Twitter. Interactions

3.3 Instagram. Followers

3.4 Instagram. Interactions

3.5 LinkedIn. Followers

3.6 LinkedIn. Interactions

4. Key communications and disseminations SURE - Farm documents. Trend 2019 - 2021

4.1 File downloads (web). (Since January 2019 until March 31st 2021)

2019

SURE-Farm Downloads	25/JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	TOTAL 2019
2019													
Downloads	124	182	157	240	267	227	246	148	387	309	232	195	2.714 ∞ %
Unique downloads	110	157	146	215	227	199	210	127	352	271	215	162	2.391 ∞ %

2020

SURE-Farm Downloads	25/JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	TOTAL 2020
2020													
Downloads	266	287	345	235	238	534	275	150	461	339	294	433	3.857 42%
Unique downloads	247	243	327	228	223	479	259	140	430	304	279	376	3.535 48%

2021

SURE-Farm Downloads	25/JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	TOTAL 31/3/2021
2021													
Downloads	90	138	255										483
Unique downloads	85	129	205										419

4.2 Policy and business briefs

4.2.1 Policy briefs. Downloads

POLICY BRIEF / DOCUMENT LABEL	DOWNLOADS	UNIQUE DOWNLOAD
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/D4.6_Policy-Brief-on-the-CAP-post-2020.pdf	104	98
https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/D2.5.-Policy-Brief-on-farmer-adaptive-behaviour-and-risk-management.pdf	63	58
https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Policy-Brief-1-final.pdf	55	52
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/D3.9_Policy-brief-on-farm-demographics.pdf	55	46
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/D3.9_Policy-brief-on-farm-demographics-German.pdf	48	42
https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/D3.6_Policy-brief-on-future-farm-demographics.pdf	44	40
https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/D3.3-Policy-Brief-Intergenerational-Renewal-edited.pdf	42	38
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/D3.3-Policy-Brief-Intergenerational-Renewal-edited.pdf	39	36
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/D2.5.-Policy-Brief-on-farmer-adaptive-behaviour-and-risk-management.pdf	36	34
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/D3.6_Policy-brief-on-future-farm-demographics.pdf	35	31
https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/D4.5-Policy-recommendations-for-strengthening-the-Common-Agricultural-Policy%E2%80%99s-resilience-impacts.pdf	34	33
https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/D3.9_Policy-brief-on-farm-demographics.pdf	27	23
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Policy-Brief-1-final.pdf	24	20
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/D4.5-Policy-recommendations-for-strengthening-the-Common-Agricultural-Policy%E2%80%99s-resilience-impacts.pdf	23	20

POLICY BRIEF / DOCUMENT LABEL	DOWNLOADS	UNIQUE DOWNLOAD
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/D4.3-Bottom-up-policy-analysis.pdf	18	15
https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Infographic_Policy-brief-Resilience-Framework.pdf	16	15
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/D5.7-Policy-Brief-Infographic.pdf	16	13
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/D5.7-Policy-Brief-Resilience-of-FS-under-current-conditions-and-future-scenarios.pdf	16	11
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Infographic_Policy-brief-Resilience-Framework.pdf	14	9
https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/D4.3-Bottom-up-policy-analysis.pdf	11	11
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/SUREFARM-D6.3-Policy-Brief.pdf	10	8
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/D4.3-Bottom-up-policy-analysis.pdf	7	7
https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/D4.5-Policy-recommendations-for-strengthening-the-Common-Agricultural-Policy's-resilience-impacts.pdf	3	3
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/D4.5-Policy-recommendations-for-strengthening-the-Common-Agricultural-Policy's-resilience-impacts.pdf	3	3
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Risk-Management-Policy-Brief.pdf	1	1
TOTAL	744	667

4.2.2 Policy briefs. Social media

POLICY BRIEF	DATE	LINK	TITLE	TWITTER				INSTAGRAM		LINKEDIN		
				TWEETS	LIKES	RETWEETS	CLICKS	POSTS	LIKES	POSTS	REACTIONS	CLICKS
D1.5 Policy brief on resilience framework, scenarios and farm typology	June, 18	https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Policy-Brief-1-final.pdf	Why the CAP should widen its approach to resilience	3	56	40	58			1	6	7
D2.5 Policy brief on farmer adaptive behavior and risk management in EU agriculture	September, 19	https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/D2.5-Policy-Brief-on-farmer-adaptive-behaviour-and-risk-management.pdf	Policy brief on farmer adaptive behaviour and risk management in EU agriculture	3	39	26	20	3	24			
D3.3 Policy brief on farm demographics and impacts on farm structure	August, 19	https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/D3.3-Policy-Brief-Intergenerational-Renewal-edited.pdf	Intergenerational renewal in EU-Farming Systems. What can policy do?	4	62	52	58	3	17	1	5	2
D3.6 Policy brief on future developments in farm demographics and structural change in selected regions of the EU	March, 20	https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/D3.6_Policy-brief-on-future-farm-demographics.pdf	Policy brief on future farm demographics and structural change in selected regions of the EU	2	12	7	3	1	11	1	2	10

POLICY BRIEF	DATE	LINK	TITLE	TWITTER				INSTAGRAM		LINKEDIN		
				TWEETS	LIKES	RETWEETS	CLICKS	POSTS	LIKES	POSTS	REACTIONS	CLICKS
D3.9 Policy brief on policy options for resilient farm demographics and farm structural	June, 20	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/D3.9_Policy-brief-on-farm-demographics.pdf	Policy options for resilienceenhancing farm demographics	4	38	13	22	3	18			
D4.6 Policy brief with a critical analysis of how current policies constrain/enable resilient EU agriculture	August, 20	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/D4.6_Policy-Brief-on-the-CAP-post-2020.pdf	Policy brief with a critical analysis of how current policies constrain/enable resilient European agriculture and suggestions for improvements, including recommendations for the CAP post-2020 reform	8	56	33	49	4	12	1	14	22
D5.7 Policy brief on the resilience of farming systems in the EU under current conditions and future scenarios	February, 21	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/D5.7-Policy-Brief-Resilience-of-FS-under-current-conditions-and-future-scenarios.pdf	The resilience of farmingsystems in the EU under currentconditions and future scenarios	5	41	26	20	2	23			
D6.3 Policy brief guiding principles for an enabling environment fostering resilience	February, 21	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/SUREFARM-D6.3-Policy-Brief.pdf	Principles for a resilienceenabling environment	3	15	5	2	2	17	2	71	32

4.2.3 Business briefs. Downloads

BUSINESS BRIEF / DOCUMENT LABEL	DOWNLOADS	UNIQUE DOWNLOAD
https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/D3.7-Business-Brief-Infographic.pdf	39	36
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/D3.7-Business-Brief-Infographic.pdf	35	33
TOTAL	74	69

4.2.4 Business Briefs. Social media

BUSINESS BRIEF	DATE	LINK	TITLE	TWITTER				INSTAGRAM		LINKEDIN		
				TWEETS	LIKES	RETWEETS	CLICKS	POSTS	LIKES	POSTS	REACTIONS	CLICKS
D2.7 Business brief on opportunities for improved risk management for EU agriculture	November, 19	https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/D2.7-Opportunities-for-improved-risk-management-for-EU-agriculture_EN.pdf	Four main avenues to improve risk management towards more resilient EU farming systems	11	50	29	27	2	16	1	2	6
D3.7 Business brief on farming opportunities for entrants and young farmers	May, 20	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/D3.7_English.pdf	Shifting the focus from "more" to "more successful" generational renewal	8	23	9	10	1	6	1	7	7

4.3 Video, GIFs and infographics

4.3.1 Video.

4.3.1.1.Video. Downloads

VIDEOS	DATE	LINK	WEB					
			PAGEVIEWS	UNIQUE PAGEVIEWS	AVG. TIME ON PAGE	ENTRANCES	BOUNCE RATE	DOWNLOAD
Building resilience of farming systems. How to deal with challenges	25/11/20	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dvK7gfSwpuY	25	18	0:02:42	7	43%	-

4.3.1.2 Video. Social media

DATE	TWITTER			VIDEO VIEWS	INSTAGRAM	
	LIKES	RETWEETS	CLICKS ON LINK		LIKES	VIDEO VIEWS
18/1/19	9	5	0	123	16	14
15/2/19	4	5	0	-	-	-
18/2/19	6	5	2	111	19	43
25/2/19	-	-	-	61	17	32
28/2/19	25	11	8	342	17	35
8/3/19	16	10	9	-	-	-
11/3/19	25	11	1	384	17	31
20/3/19	4	5	2	198	13	31
29/3/19	13	1	5	156	19	33
5/4/19	15	5	9	-	-	-
15/4/19	13	8	8	210	10	35
22/4/19	8	4	0	185	-	-
26/4/19	12	4	0	157	17	38
29/4/19	4	4	2	136	16	38
22/5/19	6	2	0	111	13	33

DATE	TWITTER				INSTAGRAM	
	LIKES	RETWEETS	CLICKS ON LINK	VIDEO VIEWS	LIKES	VIDEO VIEWS
2/6/19	-	-	-	-	10	27
27/6/19	11	3	0	152	-	-
3/9/19	30	29	50	1070	-	-
23/9/19	18	15	13	282	-	-
24/9/19	9	4	0	-	-	-
16/10/19	12	4	0	209	7	21
18/10/19	13	6	4	149	8	22
22/10/19	13	5	1	169	8	29
28/10/19	12	5	4	198	6	24
31/10/19	4	0	0	73	4	39
5/11/19	4	1	1	89	5	22
8/11/19	1	1	0	67	6	21
13/11/19	13	9	8	358	4	18
18/11/19	4	0	0	81	6	23
27/11/19	19	9	3	261	6	8

DATE	TWITTER				INSTAGRAM	
	LIKES	RETWEETS	CLICKS ON LINK	VIDEO VIEWS	LIKES	VIDEO VIEWS
18/12/19	13	8	19	227	-	-
20/12/19	15	8	0	216	7	4
26/12/19	8	3	2	188	-	-
3/1/20	9	1	0	119	10	54
5/2/20	7	6	9	222	9	37
19/2/20	5	5	0	135	9	59
17/3/20	7	3	1	108	5	32
19/3/20	3	0	0	69	-	-
10/4/20	2	0	0	-	-	-
16/4/20	3	1	1	58	6	19
23/4/20	-	-	-	63	-	-
30/4/20	-	-	-	-	9	24
7/5/20	3	2	3	106	-	-
15/5/20	5	2	2	75	6	21
28/5/20	-	-	-	-	3	28

DATE	TWITTER				INSTAGRAM	
	LIKES	RETWEETS	CLICKS ON LINK	VIDEO VIEWS	LIKES	VIDEO VIEWS
4/6/20	7	1	5	140	9	23
10/6/20	3	1	1	68	7	31
15/6/20	6	0	1	69	10	25
23/6/20	7	10	2	182	5	22
26/6/20	3	3	6	296	-	-
30/6/20	-	-	-	-	7	23
8/7/20	2	0	2	41	8	18
10/7/20	4	2	0	81	4	27
13/7/20	5	0	1	77	4	29
16/7/20	3	2	0	61	4	31
21/7/20	11	2	2	128	9	31
24/7/20	2	2	3	-	-	-
27/7/20	7	4	5	-	-	-
30/7/20	7	1	5	-	-	-
7/8/20	12	11	33	-	-	-
13/8/20	8	4	2	-	-	-
17/8/20	4	1	1	-	-	-
20/8/20	6	6	28	-	-	-

DATE	TWITTER				INSTAGRAM	
	LIKES	RETWEETS	CLICKS ON LINK	VIDEO VIEWS	LIKES	VIDEO VIEWS
9/10/20	6	3	3	-	-	-
12/11/20	8	3	16	-	-	-
17/11/20	7	6	0	54	-	-
23/11/20	7	2	4	188	-	-
4/12/20	9	3	0	148	5	15
11/12/20	6	0	1	46	-	-
18/12/20	-	-	-	-	4	-
24/12/20	4	3	0	-	-	-
25/1/21	7	1	0	68	5	33
3/2/21	2	1	0	35	-	-
23/2/21	-	-	-	-	5	20
30/3/21	-	-	-	-	11	31

4.3.2 GIFs

4.3.2.1 GIFs. Social media

GIFS	DATE	LINK	TWITTER				INSTAGRAM			LINKEDIN		
			TWEEETS	LIKES	RETWEETS	CLICKS ON LINK	POSTS	LIKES	VIEWS	POSTS	REACTIONS	CLICKS ON LINK
GIF on Farm Demographics	2/9/2019	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/GIF-D4.6-CAP-post2020.mp4	3	20	12	11	2	8	69	2	22	32
GIF on Risk Management	23/9/2019	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/GIF-D3.9.Farm-demographics.gif	1	10	7	8	-	-	-	1	7	4
GIF on policy options for resilience enhancing farm demographics	1/7/2020	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/GIF_2.5-Policy-Brief-on-Risk-Management.gif	1	18	15	13	-	-	-	1	6	3
GIF on the CAP post 2020	1/8/2020	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/GIF_Farm-demographics.gif	2	35	30	55	1	8	24	-	-	-
Other	-	-	1	5	4	7	-	-	-	1	12	6

4.3.3 Infographics.

4.3.3.1 Infographics. Downloads

INFOGRAPHICS / DOCUMENT LABEL	DOWNLOADS	UNIQUE DOWNLOAD
https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/D3.7-Business-Brief-Infographic.pdf	39	36
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/D3.7-Business-Brief-Infographic.pdf	35	33
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/SURE-Farm_First-Infographic_V4.pdf	33	29
https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Infographic_Policy-brief-Resilience-Framework.pdf	16	15
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/D5.7-Policy-Brief-Infographic.pdf	16	13
https://surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/SURE-Farm_First-Infographic_V4.pdf	14	13
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Infographic_Policy-brief-Resilience-Framework.pdf	14	9
https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/D6.3-Infographic.pdf	11	11
TOTAL	178	159

3.3.2 Infographics. Social media

INFOGRAPHICS	DATE	LINK	TITLE	TWITTER				INSTAGRAM		LINKEDIN		
				TWEETS	LIKES	RETWEETS	CLICKS ON LINK	POSTS	LIKES	POSTS	REACTIONS	CLICKS ON LINK
Resilience Framework	6/10/2017	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Infographic_Policy-brief-Resilience-Framework.png	Why the cap should widen its approach to resilience	4	62	43	61	3	38	2	11	9
SURE-Farm at a glance	4/6/2018	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/SURE-Farm_First-Infographic_V4.pdf		3	50	43	71	-	-	1	5	5
Improved risk management towards more resilient EU farming systems	11/12/2019	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/Business-Brief-on-improved-risk-management_Infographic-scale-d.jpg	Improved risk management towards more resilient EU farming systems	3	25	19	16	1	6	1	3	2
Future farm demographics and structural change	1/4/2020	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Infographic-Farm-Demographics-scaled.jpg	Resilient farm demographics withstand, adapt, or transform in the face of competitive pressure, technological change, and the expected lifestyles of future	1	7	4	3	1	11	1	5	10
Successful generational renewal	2/6/2020	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/D3.7-Business-Brief-Infographic.pdf	Six question to shifting the focus from more to mere successful generational renewal in farming	1	7	4	3	-	-	1	7	7
Principles for a resilience-enabling environment	15/2/2021	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/D6.3-Infographic.pdf	Guiding principles for an enabling environment fostering resilience	1	12	10	5	1	11	1	16	25
Resilience of farming systems in the EU under current conditions and future scenarios	1/3/2021	https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/D5.7-Policy-Brief-Infographic.pdf	How can sustainability an resilience be improved?	1	9	8	13	1	13	1	16	46
Otros	Varias	Varios	-	2	24	7	13	2	13	-	-	-

5. SURE - Farm Google Trend 2017 - 2021

5.1 Search trends worldwide

Web searches

News searches

5.2 Trend on SURE-Farm partner countries

5.2.1 Belgium

Web searches

News searches

5.2.2 Bulgaria

Web Searches

5.2.3 France

Web searches

News searches

5.2.4 Germany

Web searches

News searches

5.2.5 Italy

Web searches

News searches

5.2.6 The Netherlands

Web searches

News searches

5.2.7 Norway

Web searches

News searches

5.2.8 Romania

Web searches

News searches

5.2.9 Spain

Web searches

News searches

5.2.10 Sweden

Web searches

5.2.11 Switzerland

Web searches

6. Website

6.1 2017

	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	2017	
WEBSITE														
TOTAL VISITS												414	634	1.048
SESSIONS												109	273	382
REBOUND PERCENTAGE												41%	55%	51%
PAGES PER SESSION												3,8	2,32	3
SESSION' AVERAGE DURATION												0:05:29	0:01:41	0:02:46
TOTAL WEB VISITORS												61	186	230
NEW VISITORS												61	169	230
ORGANIC SESSIONS												41	99	140
DIRECT SESSIONS												60	161	221
REFERRAL SESSIONS												3	2	5

	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	2017
TRAFFIC FROM SOCIAL MEDIA													
SESSIONS FROM SOCIAL MEDIA											5	10	15
VISITORS FROM SOCIAL MEDIA											5	10	15
UNIQUE VISITORS FROM SOCIAL MEDIA											5	10	15

6.1.1 Session locations 2017

6.2 2018

	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	2.018	2018 2017
WEBSITE														
TOTAL VISITS	1.129	1.913	1.634	2.679	1.839	2.062	1.338	1.337	1.827	1.560	1.639	1.132	20.089	
SESSIONS	353	575	645	953	660	1.090	505	617	666	646	655	468	7.833	
REBOUND PERCENTAGE	41%	42%	51%	45%	52%	67%	51%	55%	46%	54%	53%	52%	52%	
PAGES PER SESSION	3,2	3,33	2,53	2,81	2,79	1,89	2,65	2,17	2,74	2,41	2,5	2,42	2,56	
SESSION AVERAGE DURATION	0:02:57	0:04:07	0:02:22	0:02:54	0:02:36	0:01:32	0:02:37	0:02:25	0:02:58	0:02:24	0:02:31	0:02:51	0:02:36	
TOTAL WEB VISITORS	229	349	378	564	447	845	377	470	378	414	477	314	4.555	
NEW VISITORS	206	310	314	477	380	758	318	408	319	346	422	270	4.528	
ORGANIC SESSIONS	150	248	295	475	352	387	263	264	371	361	315	254	3.735	
DIRECT SESSIONS	168	224	214	315	246	359	157	169	213	218	269	118	2.670	
REFERRAL SESSIONS	18	10	33	65	48	150	53	167	44	53	59	77	777	

	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH		MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	2.018	2018 2017
TRAFFIC FROM SOCIAL MEDIA														
SESSIONS FROM SOCIAL MEDIA	16	93	103	98	13	194	32	17	38	14	12	19	649	
VISITORS FROM SOCIAL MEDIA	10	62	50	80	10	182	27	10	25	12	12	17	475	
UNIQUE VISITORS FROM SOCIAL MEDIA	7	59	43	67	7	179	26	6	18	6	12	13	443	

6.2.1 Session locations 2018

6.2.3 Demographic variables visitors 2018

6.3 2019

	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	2019	2019 2018
WEBSITE														
TOTAL VISITS	1.807	1.796	1.862	1.993	2.045	1.528	1.439	1.294	2.504	2.118	1.610	1.326	21.322	6%
SESSIONS	697	651	715	801	861	582	587	571	1.040	956	790	668	8.919	14%
REBOUND PERCENTAGE	53%	48%	51%	47%	56%	43%	44%	57%	51%	52%	56%	59%	52%	
PAGES PER SESSION	2,59	2,76	2,6	2,49	2,38	2,63	2,45	2,27	2,41	2,22	2,04	1,99	2,39	-7%
SESSION' AVERAGE DURATION	0:02:53	0:03:26	0:03:07	0:02:43	0:02:55	0:03:33	0:03:30	0:02:28	0:02:59	0:02:44	0:02:29	0:01:56	0:02:53	10%
TOTAL WEB VISITORS	459	399	472	524	599	367	364	450	690	608	579	475	5.256	15%
NEW VISITORS	409	341	388	445	528	297	304	397	614	534	517	414	5.188	15%
ORGANIC SESSIONS	318	332	405	441	449	337	264	333	436	479	396	320	4.510	21%
DIRECT SESSIONS	234	202	214	255	308	166	187	177	285	325	315	263	2.931	10%
REFERRAL SESSIONS	44	23	16	10	8	47	69	35	108	36	34	13	443	-43%

	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	2019	2019 2018
TRAFFIC FROM SOCIAL MEDIA														
SESSIONS FROM SOCIAL MEDIA	101	94	80	95	96	32	67	26	145	70	45	72	923	42%
VISITORS FROM SOCIAL MEDIA	68	46	59	80	72	18	49	18	90	31	17	30	482	1%
UNIQUE VISITORS FROM SOCIAL MEDIA	58	32	45	63	56	9	36	11	68	18	8	22	426	-4%

6.3.1 Session locations 2019

6.3.3 Demographic variables visitors 2019

6.4 2020

	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	2020	2020 2019
WEBSITE														
TOTAL VISITS	2.349	1.870	2.044	1.540	1.428	2.570	1.682	1.034	1.956	1.810	1.814	1.539	21.636	1%
SESSIONS	1.216	891	989	786	715	1.101	749	517	819	845	856	538	10.022	12%
REBOUND PERCENTAGE	69%	55%	48%	59%	59%	53%	55%	59%	49%	54%	56%	57%	56%	
PAGES PER SESSION	1,93	2,1	2,07	1,96	2	2,33	2,25	2	2,39	2,14	2,12	2,86	2,16	-10%
SESSION' AVERAGE DURATION	0:01:59	0:02:18	0:02:47	0:02:04	0:02:12	0:03:19	0:02:40	0:01:56	0:02:50	0:02:47	0:02:47	0:04:30	0:02:39	-8%
TOTAL WEB VISITORS	966	650	713	569	525	681	524	394	547	536	550	366	6.446	23%
NEW VISITORS	906	574	641	524	485	625	472	354	500	485	493	315	6.374	23%
ORGANIC SESSIONS	386	388	384	357	373	474	372	298	411	460	449	282	4.634	2,75
DIRECT SESSIONS	730	386	339	333	275	421	280	170	363	329	309	173	4.108	40%
REFERRAL SESSIONS	26	42	194	60	45	81	78	31	24	42	59	35	717	62%

	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	2019	2020 2019
TRAFFIC FROM SOCIAL MEDIA														
SESSIONS FROM SOCIAL MEDIA	74	75	72	36	22	125	19	18	21	14	39	48	563	-39%
VISITORS FROM SOCIAL MEDIA	31	43	33	17	13	71	11	16	21	10	26	37	292	-39%
UNIQUE VISITORS FROM SOCIAL MEDIA	23	27	22	12	12	58	4	12	18	9	23	33	253	-41%

6.4.1 Session locations 2020

6.4.3 Demographic variables visitors 2020

6.5 2021

	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	1/1 to 31/3
WEBSITE													
TOTAL VISITS	598	1.606	2.214										4.418
SESSIONS	237	778	1.120										2.135
REBOUND PERCENTAGE	51%	57%	65%										61%
PAGES PER SESSION	2,52	2,06	1,98										2,07
SESSION' AVERAGE DURATION	0:03:25	0:02:06	0:02:19										0:02:21
TOTAL WEB VISITORS	151	532	818										1.501
NEW VISITORS	132	506	753										1.391
ORGANIC SESSIONS	87	264	489										840
DIRECT SESSIONS	102	372	477										951
REFERRAL SESSIONS	44	59	64										167

	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL, 15	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	1/1 to 31/3
TRAFFIC FROM SOCIAL MEDIA													
SESSIONS FROM SOCIAL MEDIA	4	81	89										174
VISITORS FROM SOCIAL MEDIA	3	59	74										136
UNIQUE VISITORS FROM SOCIAL MEDIA	0	52	60										112

6.5.1 Session locations 2021

6.5.3 Demographic variables visitors 2021

7. Social media

7.1 2017

SOCIAL MEDIA	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	TOTAL 2017
TWITTER													
FOLLOWERS							No activity		65	105	116	135	135
TWEETS								2	3	0	7	12	
PROFILE VISITS								-	-	-	-	-	
IMPRESSIONS								627	7.570	2.126	7.782	18.105	
MENTIONS								-	-	-	-	-	
INTERACTIONS								101	182	27	94	404	
Likes								7	57	4	42	110	
Retweets								10	48	10	42	110	
Replies								4	1	0	0	5	
Clics								21	76	13	10	120	
INSTAGRAM													
FOLLOWERS							0	No activity					0
POSTS							1						1
INTERACTIONS							4	No activity					4
VIDEO VIEWS							0						0
LIKES							4						4

7.2 2018

SOCIAL MEDIA	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	TOTAL 2018
TWITTER													
FOLLOWERS	153	176	193	260	266	313	354	371	403	412	431	442	442 227%
TWEETS	3	9	3	7	0	4	6	1	6	0	1	1	41
PROFILE VISITS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
IMPRESSIONS	6.799	15.456	9.253	21.000	3.632	13.100	7.093	4.714	9.085	2.140	3.372	4.268	92.819
MENTIONS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
INTERACTIONS	108	259	123	321	9	218	132	41	155	5	41	40	1.320
Likes	33	80	53	106	0	72	79	20	82	1	19	17	483
Retweets	19	85	29	87	0	55	35	8	42	1	9	11	346
Replies	2	2	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	1	0	15
Clics	54	92	41	128	9	81	18	13	31	3	12	12	494
INSTAGRAM													
FOLLOWERS													
POSTS													
INTERACTIONS	No activity												No activity
VIDEO VIEWS													
LIKES													

7.3 2019

SOCIAL MEDIA	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	TOTAL 2019
TWITTER													
FOLLOWERS	465	486	520	554	574	600	618	643	685	726	760	778	778 76,02%
TWEETS	8	11	13	23	15	14	13	14	17	14	15	15	172 320%
PROFILE VISITS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	237	180	156	234	807 -
IMPRESSIONS	19.871	15.624	24.769	30.500	19.003	16.830	18.135	14.353	27.180	17.515	19.020	17.174	239.974 159%
MENTION	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6	9	12	27 -
INTERACTIONS	229	220	351	419	261	198	289	175	449	246	227	248	3.312 151%
Likes	94	108	171	228	124	96	108	98	226	133	110	115	1.611 234%
Retweets	58	58	77	80	50	45	57	35	108	59	59	62	748 118%
Replies	0	0	1	2	1	1	0	1	0	2	1	2	11 -27%
Clis	77	54	102	109	86	56	124	41	115	52	57	69	942 91%
INSTAGRAM													
FOLLOWERS	14	49	64	74	75	76	74	74	80	82	83	85	85 -
POSTS	7	11	8	9	9	8	9	10	1	10	9	7	98 -
INTERACTIONS	122	196	130	155	144	73	47	53	2	41	17	44	1.024 -
VIDEO VIEWS	12	87	87	103	28	26	0	0	4	22	25	69	463 -
LIKES	121	191	127	151	139	72	47	52	1	41	17	44	1.003 -

7.4 2020

SOCIAL MEDIA	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	TOTAL 2020	
TWITTER														
FOLLOWERS	806	842	897	949	974	997	1.015	1.036	1.056	1.075	1.096	1.109	1.109	43%
TWEETS	13	14	15	16	13	13	13	16	14	13	14	17	171	-1%
PROFILE VISITS	115	203	156	333	132	348	119	141	178	82	127	753	2.687	-
IMPRESSIONS	18.290	21.982	16.492	19.800	13.702	13.620	12.710	17.515	12.090	11.718	10.320	13.826	182.065	-24%
MENTION	12	15	16	15	12	13	12	16	21	5	6	18	161	-
INTERACTIONS	181	269	155	178	121	127	146	292	144	214	120	222	2.169	-35%
Likes	92	97	76	92	63	53	84	102	81	112	56	129	1.037	-1%
Retweets	41	54	31	34	23	30	28	55	30	34	18	37	415	-45%
Replies	1	4	1	2	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	14	27%
Clics	47	114	47	50	35	44	33	134	32	67	45	55	703	-25%
INSTAGRAM														
FOLLOWERS	105	114	128	140	149	160	167	175	177	191	198	201	201	136%
POSTS	10	8	9	9	8	9	9	8	10	9	8	10	107	9%
INTERACTIONS	74	77	87	82	45	57	54	31	48	52	27	35	669	-35%
VIDEO VIEWS	0	0	0	0	28	114	124	39	0	0	0	34	339	-27%
LIKES	74	76	87	81	45	57	52	31	48	52	27	34	664	-34%

SOCIAL MEDIA	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	TOTAL 2020
LINKEDIN	2												
FOLLOWERS		39	48	54	91	117	150	178	199	209	250	300	300
POSTS		0	8	5	4	5	5	4	4	5	5	4	49
PAGE VIEWS		-	-	30	53	72	69	40	35	24	164	66	553
UNIQUE VISITORS PAGE		-	-	12	31	36	33	21	17	14	63	34	261
CLICKS		0	41	44	29	43	24	38	68	29	18	60	394
INTERACTIONS		0	28	25	38	45	28	32	50	29	22	63	360
Reactions		0	26	18	28	33	26	29	44	27	22	48	301
Shares		0	2	5	8	12	2	3	4	1	0	15	52
Comments		0	0	2	2	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	7

7.5 2021 (March 31st)

SOCIAL MEDIA	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	TOTAL 31/03/2021
TWITTER													
FOLLOWERS	1.125	1.147	1.181										1.181 6%
TWEETS	13	12	22										47
PROFILE VISITS	511	622	1.595										2.728
IMPRESSIONS	11.532	17.332	28.241										57.105
MENTIONS	3	21	23										47
INTERACTIONS	171	218	329										718
Likes	93	92	141										326
Retweets	34	49	71										154
Replies	1	0	0										1
Clics	43	77	117										237
INSTAGRAM													
FOLLOWERS	217	250	277										277 38%
POSTS	9	8	10										27
INTERACTIONS	74	58	96										228
VIDEO VIEWS	33	19	31										83
LIKES	73	58	96										227

SOCIAL MEDIA	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	TOTAL 31/03/2021
LINKEDIN	2												
FOLLOWERS	344	410	496										496 65%
POSTS	4	4	5										13
PAGE VIEWS	102	155	263										520
UNIQUE VISITORS PAGE	53	97	144										294
CLICKS	53	65	93										211
INTERACTIONS	76	67	68										211
Reactions	36	59	55										150
Shares	40	8	10										58
Comments	0	0	3										3

3 Dissemination activities.

3.1 Referred papers published

Title	Authors	Published (Journal)
The Struggle of Farming Systems in Europe: Looking for Explanations Through the Lens of Resilience	Meuwissen, M., P. Feindt, A. Spiegel, E. Mathijs, R. Finger, P. Midmore, Y. de Mey, K. Termeer, A. Balman, E. Wauters, P. Reidsma	Eurochoices Special Issue
Boerenpower: naar een veerkrachtige agrarische sector	Meuwissen, M. and P. Reidsma	In: de Zwarte, I. and J. Candel (Eds). Oplossingen voor het wereldvoedselvraagstuk. Wageningen University. In Press
A framework to assess the resilience of farming systems	Miranda P.M. Meuwissen et al., 2019.	Agricultural Systems, Volume 176.
Impact of Covid-19 on farming systems in Europe through the lens of resilience thinking,	Meuwissen et al.	Agricultural systems, Volume 191, June 2021, 103152.
Stakeholders' perspectives to improve risk management in European farming systems	Bertolozzi-Caredio, D.; Bardaji, I.; Garrido A.; Berry, R.; Bijttebier, J.; Gavrilescu, C.; Jendrzewski, B.; Meuwissen, M.; Ollendorf, F.; Pinsard, C.; Rommel, J.; Severini, S.; Soriano, B.	Journal of Rural Studies, 84, 147-161.

Economic risk assessment of the quality labels and productive efficiency	Bertolozzi-Caredio Daniele, Soriano Barbara, Bardají Isabel, Garrido Alberto	Agricultural Systems 191 (2021) 103169
Risk Management and its Role in Enhancing Perceived Resilience Capacities of Farms and Farming Systems in Europe	Spiegel, A., Soriano, B., de Mey, Y., Slijper, T., Urquhart, J., Bardaji, I., Vigani, M., Severini, S., Meuwissen, M.	Eurochoices Special Issue
Telling stories - farmers offer new insights into farming resilience	Phillipa Nicholas-Davies*, Susan Fowler, Peter Midmore,	Eurochoices Special Issue
Index insurances for grasslands – A review for Europe and North-America	WillemijnVroege, TobiasDalhaus, RobertFinger	2019. Agricultural Systems, Volume 168, Pages 101-111
Insuring Weather Risks in European Agriculture	Vroege et al.	Eurochoices Special Issue
Resilience, Labour, and Migration Trends in the EU-27	Slijper, T., et al	Eurochoices Special Issue
From risk behavior to perceived resilience: A Dutch case study	Slijper, T. Y. de Mey, P.M. Poortvliet, M.P.M. Meuwissen	X In press Ecology and Society
Key steps and dynamics of family farm succession in marginal extensive livestock farming	Bertolozzi-Caredio, Isabel Bardaji, Isabeau Coopmans, Barbara Soriano, Alberto Garrido	2020. Journal of Rural Studies, 76, 131-141. ISSN 0743-0167. Available online: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2020.04.030
Satellite support to insure farmers against extreme droughts.	Willemijn Vroege, Anton Vrieling & Robert Finger	Nature food

Role of learning in building resilience of small-mixed farming system - a Romanian case study	Monica-Mihaela Tudor, Camelia Gavrilescu, Julie Urquhart, Valentin-Mihai Bohateret, Ioan-Sebastian Bruma, Krisztina-Melinda Dobay, Daniela Matei, Lucian Tanasa	Lucrari Stiintifice Management Agricol, 2020, XXII (2), 180-188, ISSN print 1453-1410, ISSN online 2069-2307,
How much farm succession is enough?	Christine Pitson, Jo Bijttebier, Franziska Appel, Alfons Balmann	Eurochoices special issue
Does the Common Agricultural Policy enhance farming systems' resilience? Applying the Resilience Assessment Tool (ResAT) to a farming system case study in the Netherlands	Yannick Buitenhuis, Jeroen Candel, Katrien Termeer, Peter H. Feindt	Journal of Rural Studies Volume 80, pp. 314-327
Improving the resilience-enabling capacity of the Common Agricultural Policy: Policy recommendations for more resilient EU farming systems.	Y. Buitenhuis, J. Candel, P.H. Feindt, K. Termeer, E. Mathijs, I. Bardají, J. Black, A. Martikainen, M. Moeyersons, A. Sorrentino.	Eurochoices Special Issue
The Perception of Importance and Performance of Private and Public Functions Delivered by a Farming System – The Case Study of Horticulture Sector in Poland	Krupin V., Bańkowska K.	Annals of Polish Association of Agricultural Economists and Agribusiness, 2020, XXII (2), 125-133, DOI: 10.5604/01.3001.0013.8453.
Assessing the Resilience and Sustainability of a Hazelnut Farming System in Central Italy with a Participatory Approach.	Nera, E.; Paas, W.; Reidsma, P.; Paolini, G.; Antonioli, F.; Severini, S.	2020. Sustainability, 12, 343. Available online: https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/12/1/343

Participatory assessment of sustainability and resilience of three specialized farming systems	Wim Paas, Isabeau Coopmans, Simone Severini, Martin van Ittersum, Miranda Meuwissen, Pytrik Reidsma	Ecology & Society, 16(2):2
How do stakeholders perceive the sustainability and resilience across farming systems in the EU?	Reidsma, P., M. Meuwissen, F. Accatino, F. Appel, I. Bardaji, I. Coopmans, C. Gavrilescu, F. Heinrich, V. Krupin, G. Manevska, M. Peneva, J. Rommel, S. Severini, B. Soriano, J. Urquhart, K. Zawalinska, W. Paas	Eurochoices Special Issue
Stability of risk attitude, agricultural policies and production shocks: evidence from Italy.	Bozzola, M., Finger, R.	European Review of Agricultural Economics (2020) pp. 1–25
The optimal drought index for designing weather index insurance	Bucheli, J., Dalhaus, T., Finger, R.	European Review of Agricultural Economics (2020) pp. 1–25
Effects of the Income Stabilization Tool on farm income level, variability and concentration in Italian agriculture	Severini S., Di Tommaso G., Finger R. (2019)	Agricultural and Food Economics. 7:23. Page:1-22. https://doi.org/10.1186/s40100-019-0141-9
Modeling agricultural risk management policies – The implementation of the Income Stabilization Tool in Italy”.	Severini S., Biagini L. and Finger R. (2019)	Journal of Policy Modeling, 41(1): 140-155. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpolmod.2018.03.003
Human behaviour versus optimising agents and the resilience of farms – Insights from agent-based participatory experiments with FarmAgriPoliS	Appel, F., Balmann, A. 2019.	Ecological Complexity 40 Part B. Available online: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecocom.2018.08.005

Institutions and the resilience of biobased production systems: the historical case of livestock intensification in the Netherlands.	Termeer, C.J.A.M., Feindt, P.H., Karpouzoglou, T., Poppe, K.J., Hofstede, G., Kramer, K., Ge, L., Matthijs, E., Meuwissen, M.P.M., 2019.	Ecology and Society 24 (4):15. https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-11206-240415 .
Creating a market for price swaps: Case study of an innovative risk management instrument in the Belgian-Dutch pear market	Eewoud Lievens, Kobe Tielens, Erik Mathijs	Agricultural Economics – Czech, 67, 2021 (1): 33–40
Badanie żywotności systemów produkcji rolnej w ramach SURE-Farm H2020 (Study of Endurance of Agricultural Production Systems in the Framework of SURE-Farm H2020, in Polish language)	Krupin V., Bańkowska K.	Annals of Polish Association of Agricultural Economists and Agribusiness, 2017, XIX (2): 127-132, DOI: 10.5604/01.3001.0010.1172
Shared socio-economic pathways for European agriculture: Eur-Agri-SSPs	Mitter, H., A.-K. Techen, F. Sinabell, K. Helming, K. Kok, J. Priess, B. Bodirsky, I. Holman, H. Lehtonen, A. Leip, C. Le Mouël, E. Mathijs, B. Mehdi, M. Michetti, K. Mittenzwei, O. Mora, L. Øygarden, P. Reidsma, R. Schaldach, E. Schmid, M. Schoenhart	Global Environmental Change, in press
A protocol to develop Shared Socio-economic Pathways for European agriculture	Mitter, H., A.-K. Techen, F. Sinabell, K. Helming, K. Kok, J. Priess, B. Bodirsky, I. Holman, H. Lehtonen, A. Leip, C. Le Mouël, E. Mathijs, B. Mehdi, M. Michetti, K. Mittenzwei, O. Mora, L. Øygarden, P. Reidsma, R. Schaldach, E. Schmid, M. Schoenhart	2019. Journal of Environmental Management 252, 109701.

3.2 Attendance to congress/ conferences and dissemination events

Conference /Meeting	Date	Session	Participants
Uppsala EAAE seminar, M.Meuwissen	07/02/2019	A behavioural perspective on resilience of farming systems	50
Presentation PhD students @ Wageningen University, M. Meuwissen	11/02/2019	SURE-Farm framework	25
Stakeholder workshop in Widniówka, Poland (FoPIA 1)	06/03/2019	Presentation of the SURE-Farm project to stakeholders	20
93rd Annual Conference, Warwick University, Coventry, UK	15-17 April 2019	Poster paper "Farm business resilience in East Anglia: a biographical narrative analysis" (Nicholas, Midmore and Fowler) delivered at the 93rd Annual Conference, April 15-17, 2019, Warwick University, Coventry, UK	25
4TU DeSIRE conference on Resilience Engineering; Building Connections for Resilience Engineering Solutions, University of Twente, the Netherlands, Meuwissen, Keynote	07/06/2019	"The resilience of EU farming systems"	60
XXIV Workshops of Agricultural Economists, Krasnobród, Poland	10/06/2019	Presentation "Analysis of farming system's resilience based on horticulture sector in Poland" by Vitaliy Krupin (IRWiR PAN)	30
Sure-farm stakeholder workshop, Merelbeke, Flanders	05/09/2019	presentation: Index-gebaseerde weersverzekeringen. W. Vroege, E. Wauters, R. Finger	25
Congreso de Economía Agraria.La sostenibilidad agroterritorial desde la Europa Atlántica	05/09/2019	Las estrategias de gestión de riesgos y la sostenibilidad de la ganadería extensiva en España by Bárbara Soriano	15

171th EAAE Seminar- Measuring and evaluating farm income and well-being of farm families in Europe. Towards a shared and broader approach for analysis and policy design, Tänikon, Switzerland	05/09/2019	Insuring crops from space - a soil moisture approach based on satellites. W. Vroege, J. Bucheli, T. Dalhaus, M. Hirschi, R. Finger	50
173th EAAE Seminar- Sustainable and resilient farming systems in the European Union, Bucharest, Romania	26/09/2019	Potential impacts and financial sustainability of the Income Stabilization Tool. An application to hazelnut production in Italy by Severini Simone; Cinzia Zinnanti ; Emanuele Schimmenti	18
173th EAAE Seminar- Sustainable and resilient farming systems in the European Union, Bucharest, Romania	26/09/2019	Exploring attributes of resilience: robustness, adaptability and transformation in European farmer narratives Nicholas-Davies P., Fowler S., Midmore P., Coopmans I., Draganova M., Petitt A. and Senni S.	18
173th EAAE Seminar- Sustainable and resilient farming systems in the European Union, Bucharest, Romania	26/09/2019	The role of agricultural risk management in strengthening farming systems' resilience: results from a multi-scale co-creation approach by Bárbara Soriano	18
173th EAAE Seminar- Sustainable and resilient farming systems in the European Union, Bucharest, Romania	26/09/2019	A dynamic perspective to farming system resilience and its trade-off by Hugo Herrera and Birgit Kopainsky	18
173th EAAE Seminar- Sustainable and resilient farming systems in the European Union, Bucharest, Romania	26/09/2019	Perceived resilience capacities across EU farmers by Alisa Spiegel	18
Conference EAAP 2019 - Ghent, Belgium	27/08/2019	Presentation: Assessing and comparing social and biophysical trade-offs in an extensive beef cattle system region. F. Accatino, D. Neumeister, M. Tichit. Session about livestock and social perceptions	50

173th EAAE Seminar- Sustainable and resilient farming systems in the European Union, Bucharest, Romania	27/09/2019	Presentation: The adaptability of an extensive beef cattle system to contrasted social preferences - coupling multi-objective analysis and a participatory approach. F. Accatino, D. Neumeister, W. Paas, A. Tonda, P. Reidsma.	15
Ecosystem services partnership 2018 regional conference, San Sebastian, Spain	16/10/2019	Presentation: Multifunctionality of ecosystem services and resilience attributes in a gradient of agroecosystems across Europe. C Pinsard, F. Accatino, M. Tichit	40
Topsector meeting 'High Risk', World Horti Center, Naaldwijk, The Netherlands, Meuwissen.	07/11/2019	Resilience in 11 EU regions	40
173th EAAE Seminar- Sustainable and resilient farming systems in the European Union, Bucharest, Romania	26/09/2019	Spoken paper "How farmers' life stories can help to understand their management of critical decision point" (Nicholas, Midmore and Fowler) presented at the 173rd EAAE Seminar on Sustainable and resilient farming systems in the EU, Bucharest, 26-27 September 2019.	25
173th EAAE Seminar- Sustainable and resilient farming systems in the European Union, Bucharest, Romania	26/09/2019	Presentation: A participatory assessment of the sustainability and resilience of EU farming systems. W.H. Paas, Francesco Accatino, Franziska Appel, Isabel Barbaji, Isabeau Coopmans, Paul Courtney, Camelia Gavrilescu, Florian Heinrich, Vitaly Krupin, Gordana Manevska-Tasevska, Mariya Peneva, Jens Rommel, Simone Severini, Bárbara Soriano, Julie Urquhart, Erwin Wauters, Katarzyna Zawalińska, M.P.M. Meuwissen, P. Reidsma	25
173th EAAE Seminar- Sustainable and resilient farming systems in the European Union, Bucharest, Romania	26/09/2019	Presentation: Stakeholder assessment of the resilience of the Flemish dairy farming system - An application of the FoPIA-SureFarm method. Coopmans Isabeau, J. Bijttebier, Becking Jorrit, W.H. Paas, P. Reidsma, Erwin Wauters	25

173th EAAE Seminar- Sustainable and resilient farming systems in the European Union, Bucharest, Romania	26/09/2019	Understanding European farm demographic change processes and influencing factors – qualitative findings from a multiple case study approach. Isabeau Coopmans, J. Dessein, J. Bijttebier, F. Accatino, F. Antonioli, C. Gavrilescu, P. Gradziuk, G. Manevska-Tasevska, M. Meuwissen, M. Peneva, A., B. Soriano, J. Urquhart, E. Wauters	
173th EAAE Seminar- Sustainable and resilient farming systems in the European Union, Bucharest, Romania	27/09/2019	Insuring crops from space - a soil moisture approach based on satellites. W. Vroege, J. Bucheli, T. Dalhaus, M. Hirschi, R. Finger	25
Department of Land Economy, University of Cambridge	16/10/2019	“Exploring Attributes of Resilience: Robustness, Adaptability and Transformation in East Anglian Farmer Narratives” (Nicholas, Midmore and Fowler) to the Department of Land Economy, University of Cambridge, 16 October 2019	25
IV KNOWLEDGE AND INNOVATION FORUM (IV FORUM WIEDZY I INNOWACJI), Warsaw, Poland	13-14.11.2019	Presentation of the SURE-Farm poster by Katarzyna Bańkowska and Błażej Jendrzewski (IRWiR PAN)	200
CERS IE-HAS Conference "Transition in Agriculture – Agricultural Economics in Transition XVI", Budapest, Hungary	15/11/2019	Presentation "Resilience of horticulture farming in Poland: SURE-Farm H2020 approach and collected evidence" by Vitaliy Krupin (IRWiR PAN)	40
Stakeholder workshop in Puławy, Poland (FoPIA 2)	29/11/2019	Presentation of the SURE-Farm project to stakeholders	12
Meeting with insurers and researchers before the XII Convegno Nazionale su Gestione del rischio in agricoltura - Assisi (PG)	30/01/2020	Potential impacts and financial sustainability of the Income Stabilization Tool. An application to hazelnut production in Italy by Severini Simone; Cinzia Zinnanti ; Emanuele Schimmenti	40
Newbie H2020 event 'New entrants and their environments for dialogue'	04/02/2020	Presentation & group discussion: Factors that influence farm entry, exit, non-entry and non-exit decisions (Moderator: Isabeau Coopmans)	15
Meeting with stakeholders (for the French case study)	14/02/2019	Presentation of the SURE-Farm project to stakeholders before the French FoPIA-SURE-Farm workshop 1	30

ECPR General Conference 2019, Wroclaw, Poland	06/09/2019	Framework for Assessing Policy Influence on Resilience: A Case Study of the EU's Common Agricultural Policy in De Veenkoloniën, the Netherlands. Buitenhuis, Y., Candel, J. J. L., Termeer, C. J. A. M., & Feindt, P. H.	
173th EAAE Seminar- Sustainable and resilient farming systems in the European Union	26/09/2019	Framework for Assessing Policy Influence on Resilience: A Case Study of the EU's Common Agricultural Policy in De Veenkoloniën, the Netherlands. Buitenhuis, Y., Candel, J. J. L., Termeer, C. J. A. M., & Feindt, P. H.	
SURE-Farm dissemination event for Flemish dairy sector stakeholders: presentations and discussions based on WP 2, 3 and 4	16/12/2019	All sessions (event tied exclusively to SURE-Farm)	22
SURE-Farm policy workshop for Flemish stakeholders: presentation and discussion based on WP 4	17/09/2019	All sessions (event tied exclusively to SURE-Farm)	14
European research night	12/04/2019	Presentation of SURE-Farm goals, results and impacts and organized a participatory activity to co-create resilience enabling conditions for extensive sheep farming in Spain.Madrid. Daniele Bertolozzi and Bárbara Soriano	20
Science and innovation week	14/11/2019	Presentation of SURE-Farm goals, results and impacts and organized a participatory activity to co-create resilience enabling conditions for extensive sheep farming in Spain.Madrid. Bárbara Soriano and Daniele Bertolozzi	45
COP25	12/12/2019	Presentation of SURE-Farm (video, brochures, roll-up and infographics). Madrid. Bárbara Soriano and Daniele Bertolozzi	80
Francqui Chair, Université catholique de Louvain	10/03/2020	Metrics for sustainable food economies	100
Francqui Chair, Université catholique de Louvain,	27/04/2020	Policies for sustainable food economies	50
Francqui Chair, Université catholique de Louvain	04/05/2020	Transition towards sustainable and resilient food economies: how to intervene in complex systems, online	200

XVI European society for agronomy congress	9/1/2020	Sustainability and resilience of farming systems. Pytrik Reidsma (keynote speaker)	100
XVI European society for agronomy congress	9/1/2020	Participatory assessment of future sustainability and resilience of European farming systems - Wim Paas (Oral presentation)	25
Virtual meeting with operational groups for rural development	10/26/2020	SURE-Farm presentation	100
International seminar on resilience of European agricultural systems in time of COVID-19 (online. IRWIR-PAN). Miranada Mewissen, Bárbara Soriano, Franziska Appel, Gordana Manevska Tasevska, Camelia Gavrilescu and Kasia Aawalinska	12/7/2020	CS presentations on COVID-19 impact	52
Joint International Resilience Conference (online). Miranda Meuwissen, Peter Feindt, Alisa Spiegel, et al.	11/25/2020	Impact Of Covid19 on Farming Systems in Europe Through The Lens of Resilience Thinking.	20
Joint International Resilience Conference (online). Isabeau Coopmans and Erwin Wauters	11/25/2020	Impact of Covid19 on Belgian Dairy sector. Audience: 20p.	20
Seminar on Strengthening resilience in the food supply chain-DEFRA. Peter Feindt	12/7/2020	How can public policies enhance farming systems resilience	60
EAAP conference (on line), Francesco Accatino, Delphine Neumeister, Corentin Pinsard, Christèle Pineau	12/4/2020	Presentation: "Assessing sustainability and resilience of a French beef cattle system	60
Dissemination seminar organized by F. Accatino, D. Neumeister, C. Pineau	12/11/2020	Dissemination and restitution seminar: insights from the activities on the French case study + comparison with other case studies	12
CAP programming for Germany organized by the German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture	2/18/2021	Competitiveness	150
Dissemination Spanish CS resilience assessment. Alberto Garrido, Isabel Bardají, José María Sumpsi, Carolina San Martín, Daniele Bertolozzi-Caredio, Bárbara Soriano	2/26/2021	Reilience assessment of the extensive sheep farming	81

SWOT analysis-Value chain in the extensive sheep sector in Spain. Bárbara Soriano	3/10/2021	Policy recommendations to enhance resilience of the extensive sheep farming	92
EAAE webinar. Miranda Meuwissen, Bárbara Soriano, Alfons Balmann, Peter Feindt, Pytrik Reidsma, Tassos Hanriotis, Marion Picot	3/17/2021	Policy recommendations to enhance resilience of farming systems in Europe	97
Final Scientific Seminar	5/18/2021	SURE-Farm project	94
Dissemination Polish CS resilience assessment.	5/10/2021	Zwiększenie odporności europejskich systemów rolniczych (na podstawie rezultatów projektu SURE-FARM H2020)	38

